

AN INTEGRATED METHODOLOGY FOR FULL-FIELD IMAGING AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF COMPLEX COMPOSITE SUBSTRUCTURES

J. S. Callaghan¹, O. T. Thomsen², J. M. Dulieu-Barton³, and S. Laustsen⁴

¹ School of Engineering, University of Southampton, Southampton, UK, j.s.callaghan@soton.ac.uk

² School of Engineering, University of Southampton, Southampton, UK, O.Thomsen@soton.ac.uk

³ School of Engineering, University of Southampton, Southampton, UK, janice@soton.ac.uk

⁴ Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy, Aalborg, Denmark, steffen.laustsen@siemensgamesa.com

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ABSTRACT

A “pixel-matching” method is described that is used to compare and combine multi-modal full-field data from experimental and numerical sources, by spatially aligning and interpolating to a common resolution. A wind turbine blade (WTB) substructure is used as a demonstrator that is loaded in three-point bending. Experimental results are captured using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) and Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA), and numerical predictions are made using Finite Element Analysis (FEA), from which surface data is extracted. The datasets are fused using various metrics and analysed for features that will be used to discern improvements in the experiments and numerical analyses. This method will help to develop high-fidelity substructural testing procedures that will reduce the design and development time and cost of WTBs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite wind turbine blades (WTBs) are currently validated and certified following a “testing pyramid” approach, which relies heavily on time-consuming and costly coupon-scale testing for design, and is ultimately dependent on full-scale testing to achieve certification (Figure 1).

It is proposed to integrate high-fidelity structural tests with detailed finite element analyses (FEA) on the substructure-scale level to provide a means of mitigating the costs and reducing time to market for new WTB designs. Substructural testing can provide crucial data/understanding of local damage onset and failure behaviour, thus enabling accurate calibration and validation of FEA models [1]. This has the potential to reduce the number of physical tests required at the coupon scale, and to eliminate the need for full-scale structural tests altogether. Substructural testing has previously been conducted, but a systematic methodology for the integration of multiple full-field data sources has not been previously established.

Figure 1: “Testing pyramid” for wind turbine blades, with the proposed methodology in red

An initial study was conducted on a “T-joint” WTB substructure, which is the region where the internal shear web joins to the spar cap along the radial length of the WTB. The FE model and experimental setup of the T-joint involves a three-point-bending load case in tension (pull-out) and compression.

2 METHODOLOGY

Imaging techniques, including Digital Image Correlation (DIC) and Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA), and FEA modelling are all full-field analysis techniques. DIC utilises white light images to correlate greyscale pattern region locations to determine surface displacements, from which strains are derived [2]. For TSA, an infrared camera is used to obtain the changes in surface temperature (ΔT) for a cyclically loaded elastic body, which is directly related to the change of the sum of the principal stresses by a material parameter, known as the thermoelastic constant K [3].

Together, DIC, TSA, and FEA can be considered to provide “cooperative” data [4]. Combining the data using “data fusion” techniques enables the characterisation of complex structures in a new way to enhance what could be obtained by each method independently. The potential uses and advantages of a data fusion approach have been previously demonstrated [5], [6].

In this research, a technique is presented for spatially aligning the cooperative data sets, and then interpolating to match the lowest data resolution, so that all data sets can be compared and combined (fused) at every data point (“pixel matching”). The fused data facilitates the validation of numerical models from a single experiment, which is greatly beneficial for complex structural testing. The fused data also allows for a multi-modal evaluation of structural features, as the data created is richer than that recorded by any individual experimental method.

Typically full-field data is processed in one of two formats: gridded array (GA) and coordinate-based vector (CV) (Figure 2). To align the data, which may not have any associated geometric information, markers were placed on the specimens which could be picked up by the two camera types. These were placed in known locations and could be identified digitally, which allows for alignment of all datasets (Figure 3a).

Figure 2: Visualisation of data types: (a) Gridded array (GA), (b) Coordinate-based vector (CV)

The nature of the datasets means that the data points are in different locations (Figure 3b), and can therefore not be compared on a point-wise basis. Therefore, the fields are interpolated using cubic functions to match the point-wise locations of the dataset with the lowest resolution in a gridded format. Datasets can be compared using various metrics, such as by residual, relative and absolute percentage difference, and structural similarity, which allow for different interpretations of the comparison. The metrics used in this study are shown in Table 1, for the combination of two datasets f_1 and f_2 . Different metrics will allow for the identification of different features, as large magnitude differences may not be proportional to the corresponding relative differences. Ideally, the numerical model accurately predicts the real load response, and the experiment recreates the designed load case. Therefore, the fused field analysis provides feedback to both methods, by identifying differences that can be characterised and hence corrected/compensated for. The closer the combined field values are to zero, the closer the numerical model and the experimental data correspond to each other absolutely and relatively. Both experimental and simulation data are inherently influenced by uncertainty, and the data fusion enables uncertainty quantification, as both model and physical uncertainty can be assessed in the process.

Figure 3: Dataset spatial alignment: (a) dataset extremities aligned to datum origin, (b) data points located within the data point window

Metric	Formula	Explanation
Residual (Res)	$f_1 - f_2$	Difference between fields $Res > 0, f_1 > f_2$ $Res < 0, f_1 < f_2$
Relative percentage change (RPC)	$\left(\frac{f_1 - f_2}{f_2}\right) \cdot 100$	Relative difference between similar fields. The percentage difference between f_1 and f_2 in percentage amount of f_2 , i.e. $f_1 = f_2 + RPC\% (f_2)$
Absolute percentage difference (APD)	$\left \frac{f_1 - f_2}{\left(\frac{f_1 + f_2}{2}\right)}\right \cdot 100$	Absolute difference between similar fields, without reference to any particular field

Table 1: Metrics for fused datasets

3 INITIAL DEMONSTRATION

A T-joint sample was modelling numerically using ANSYS Mechanical from 20-node brick elements with data supplied from the manufacturer assuming a static loading of 8 kN and elastic conditions. An experiment was conducted on the T-joint using a servo-hydraulic test machine and a custom designed load rig. The DIC test was conducted assuming quasi-static conditions from 0 to 8 kN loading, and the TSA data was captured during a cyclic test with a load of 5 ± 4 kN. The fused datasets have a spatial resolution of 1.570 mm/data point.

When comparing the surface strain sum data for FEA and DIC (Figure 4), the large percentage difference in the u-shaped core region is attributed to incorrect material data (as supplied) used in the FEA model. Another identified feature is the warped bending axis which is clear in the residual plot, which is due to an uneven load introduction during the experiment.

Figure 4: Comparison of surface strain sum $|\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy}|$ for FEA and DIC; (a) Residual (Res), (b) Absolute percentage difference (APD)

Figure 5: Comparison of normalised surface stress sum $|\sigma_{xx} + \sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{zz}|_{norm}$ for FEA and normalised temperature change ΔT_{norm} for TSA (normalised at $[x, y] = [0, 5]$); (a) Residual (Res), (b) Absolute percentage difference (APD)

The normalised change in surface temperature (from TSA) is compared to the normalised surface stress data (from FEA) (Figure 5). The match is generally good, however, there is a difference within the central region. The maximum change of stress (~temperature) occurs in the outer spar cap, and therefore the normalisation for the FEA and TSA data is relative to the maximum value at this point. The normalised values assume that K is homogeneous across the structure, as the K data is unknown for

the various materials. Therefore, in regions made of different material to the spar cap, the comparative absolute percentage difference should be proportional to the K values for the spar cap and the triangular fillet. This data can be used to inform model updating aiming to reduce the deviations between predictions and experimental observations.

4 NUMERICAL PARAMETER SENSITIVITY

Another use of this comparative method is to assess the global response sensitivity to material parameter differences within the numerical model. The material in the u-shaped core region has been altered following the comparison from the initial demonstration to be less compliant. The two datasets (materials v0 and v1, Table 2) were matched to the DIC data mask and compared to one another for the ϵ_{xx} field.

The residual and relative percentage change plots show that the difference in the material properties has a significant effect on the whole structure (Figure 6). A more compliant core (in v0) obviously results in a greater strain through the core, however, in the bottom corners this is not true, and the strain is actually reduced when compared to a stiffer core.

The bending axis in the spar cap is shifted slightly, and the magnitude of strain is greater in v0, as the core provides less rigidity. This data can be used to inform the model updating to better predict the real specimen.

Identifier	Detail	E_{xx} (MPa)	E_{yy} (MPa)	E_{zz} (MPa)	ν_{xy}	ν_{yz}	ν_{xz}	G_{xy} (MPa)	G_{yz} (MPa)	G_{xz} (MPa)
v0	supplied by manufacturer	150	150	150	0.25	0.25	0.25	60	60	60
v1	wood data tables	6500	810	810	0.42	0.71	0.42	857	236	857

Table 2: Core material elastic properties

Figure 6: Comparison of numerical data ϵ_{xx} with different u-shaped core properties: (a) Residual, (b) Relative percentage change

5 CONCLUSIONS

A new approach to data fusion is proposed, where a pixel-matching method is adopted for discerning differences between full-field DIC, TSA, and FEA data for a WTB composite substructure subjected to various load states. It is demonstrated that the data fusion approach enables the identification of zones where improvement/refinement of the numerical modelling, as well as the experimental set-up, can be made. This will enable numerical parametric analyses to assist with the validation of material properties and failure behaviour on the substructural scale, thus reducing the dependence on the top and bottom tiers of the WTB testing pyramid for certification. Further, the data fusion procedures can be used for

efficient assessment and quantification of the inherent uncertainties associated with both the experimental and simulation data.

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